

Probiotics in Ayurvedic Concept with Special Reference to Sandhan Kalpana

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ABSTRACT

Probiotics are living or a viable bacterium which acts as supplementary microorganism that exhibit beneficial health effect on the host's health by enhancing its gastrointestinal microbial balance and have been involved in imperative biological functions such as immune system homeostasis, regulation of host metabolism, prevention of pathogens invasion and improvement of the epithelial barrier function. In Ayurveda, these compounds include Arishta (fermented decoction) and Asava (fermented infusion) obtained from polyherbal formulations. Though the occurrence of probiotic bacteria in Arishta and Asava were studied, their roles are still unknown. Although the traditional literature on Fermented Traditional Medicines (FTMs) is available with a focus on its relevance to modern science, there were no major efforts to explore the role of microflora ingested along with the medicine. In the present article, efforts have been made to search the compounds which are prepared by fermentation (Sandhan Kalpana) and have been found to influence the gut flora including the motility and have been used in various gut disorders to selectively refer them as Ayurvedic probiotics. Efforts are also been made to give references of steps involved in the preparation of these products by using the concepts behind them.

Keywords: Probiotic, fermentation, Dravya, Sandhan Kalpana, Asavsarishta.

INTRODUCTION

The human body is inhabited by trillions of dynamic and diverse microbial communities that potentially regulate the physiology of the host, popularly known as the "Microbiome". The human microbiome performs imperative biological functions such as immune system homeostasis, regulation of host metabolism, prevention of pathogens invasion and improvement of the epithelial barrier function¹The microbiome can modulate multiple cellular events such as host physiology, cellular metabolism, and immune function. Disturbance in the host-microbiota is often associated with pathological conditions such as inflammatory bowel diseases (IBS) and cancer².

United Nations World Health Organization, according to which probiotics are redefined as "live microorganisms which when administered in adequate amounts confer a health benefit on the host."

In relation to food the definition can be adjusted by emphasizing that the beneficial effect is exerted by the microorganisms "when consumed in adequate amounts as part of food"³

In order for a potential probiotic strain to be able to exert its beneficial effects, it is expected to exhibit certain desirable properties. The ones currently determined by in vitro tests are

- i. acid and bile tolerance which seems to be crucial for oral administration,
- ii. adhesion to mucosal and epithelial surfaces, an important property for successful immune modulation, competitive exclusion of pathogens, as well as prevention of pathogen adhesion and colonisation,
- iii. antimicrobial activity against pathogenic bacteria,

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iv. bile salt hydrolase activity.

Nevertheless, the value of these parameters is still under debate as there are matters of relevance, in vivo and in vitro discrepancies, and lack of standardization of operating procedures to be considered. As there are no specific parameters essential to all probiotic applications, the best approach to establish a strain's properties is target population and target physiologic function specific studies^{4,5,6}

Sandhana kalpana (biomedical fermented formulations) are one of the best dosage forms of Ayurveda in practice since thousands of years. The formulations prepared by *Sandhan Kalpana* are primarily acidic or alcoholic in nature and have been selectively used in various gut disorders. They are also referenced by various Acharyas for maintaining gut health and normal wellbeing of the mankind. They are called *Asava* and *Arishta* and in order to prepare these medicaments, certain sets of conditions are prearranged, which lead to fermentation.

Gut Microbiota:

Several bacterial genera are used in probiotic preparations, including *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium*, *Enterococcus*, *Escherichia*, *Streptococcus* and *Bacillus*. Along with this, certain fungal strains such as *Sacchromyces* are also used for probiotic application,⁷. The efficacy of probiotics depends on species, dose, clinical disease and duration of application⁸ and therefore sometimes it is required to add certain specific probiotic strains to provide health benefits. *Lactobacillus* spp. are naturally present in several fermented food products. Such as *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* which are present in yoghurt.⁹ Sauerkraut is a product of cabbage fermented by lactic acid bacteria and contains a large proportion of *Lactobacillus* spp.¹⁰. Kimchi is a popular fermented food of Korea containing high level of lactic acid bacteria such as, *Lactobacillus plantarum*¹¹. Soymilk, Kefir and several other food products provides *Lactobacillus* as natural probiotic bacteria^{12,13}. In addition, several *Lactobacillus* supplements are also available in markets for health benefits.

Probiotics in Ayurvedic Context

Heller *et al.* supplemented the techniques of ancient India to prepare *Sandhana kalpana* as a result of current findings of probiotic bacteria. These bacteria are mainly found in fermented foods, and dairy products, which play a predominant role as carriers of various other health benefits. Among these dosage forms, '*Sandhana kalpana*' is a unique form in which acidic and alcoholic fermented formulations are prepared¹⁴. In order to manufacture these medicines, liquid basic drugs (juices or decoctions) are kept for fermentation as indicated in the classics. In this process, self-generated (in these dosage forms) ethyl alcohol is produced by in-source material used in pharmaceutical procedure, and is not added from outside. Here, ethyl alcohol is not the only product yielded but is a part of many other organic compounds; further, alcohol/acetic acid (as per desired indications) is formulated and extraction of active principles of the herbal drugs is done. Thus, these formulations have longer shelf life, quick absorption and action and excellent therapeutic efficacy as compared to other Ayurvedic herbal medicines¹⁵.

History of *Sandhana kalpana*

Chronologically, the fermentation technique may be revealed in each period of Indian civilization, ie, from *Vedic* period to till date. Even this is true on record that alcoholic drinks are well known to men from the Paleolithic age. Maple fruits, bark of tree, cereals, etc were used to formulate these drinks. In *Vedic* rituals, the knowledge of fermentation was advanced. *Sura* was used as food and in divine, evening offerings. In the Neolithic period, cereal eating civilization was well known to prepare fermented drink by using cooked cereals. In the Egyptian civilization, it was an important drink in their routine life¹⁶.

In Ayurvedic science, these drugs are formulated in such a way that the alcohol-soluble extractives of herbal drugs are preserved in self-generated alcohol and used as medicines. On the other side, in European countries, different healthy drinks such as wine and beer are formulated as stimulants, used for the pleasure and enjoyment. The basic principles to prepare fermented products are fundamentally similar

from those prevalent in the ancient time to modern era. The difference observed is in the use of equipment, type of raw drugs, sterilization techniques, and preparation methods. Evolution is noted in testing parameters and also quality standards of the finished products.

Vedic period: Literary evidence from *Vedic* literature gives a clear idea about the confirmation of the existence of fermentation process. *Vedas* such as *Rigveda*, *Yajurveda*, and *Atharvaveda* have focused on various fermented formulations prepared in wooden containers. The sweet liquid *Somarasa* is a unique formulation, which is supposed to be a product obtained with the help of the fermentation technique. In *Rigveda*, along with *Somarasa* (*Rigveda* -2/14/01), another alcoholic drink *Sura* was prepared by fermentation process. *Somarasa* was used as an offering to God and *Sura* (*Rigveda* -6/66/10) was for human consumption. The people in this period were well known for the production of an acidic fermented product curd, which was routinely used in the daily diet¹⁷.

Post Vedic period: In this period, addition of new techniques and development in the preparation of fermented products took place such as grape and sugarcane, juice of *Kharjura*, bark of herbal trees, etc were added, along with rice, barley and cereals, fruits as these formulations were advocated as medicines. The use of honey, flower of *Madhuka* (*Madhuca longifolia* Koen.), *Dhataki* (*Woodfordia fruticosa*)¹⁸.

Vrihat trayee (Three great classics of Ayurveda - *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Ashtanga Hridaya*)

The good properties and adverse effects of *Sandhana* (fermented) formulations are explored to compile information regarding ancient methods of preparation of fermented drugs and other related information. It is revealed that ‘*Madya*’ term was used for alcoholic drink. Referred authors found many innovations in this period, which were introduced by Ayurvedic scholars for preparation of *Sandhana kalpana*¹⁹.

1. Charaka Samhita

In this period, several original revelations were made about preparation of different herbal formulations as

medicines. Literary review says that several *AsavaArishta* were well known to physicians during that period. *Charaka Samhita* explains that especially the nine herbal sources— *Phala* (fruits), *Dhanya* (cereals), *Mula* (roots), *Pushpa* (flowers), *Twak* (bark), *Sara* (exudate), *Kanda* (branches), *Patra* (leaves), and *Sharkara* (sugar) for the preparation of fermented medicines, definition of fermentation, specification in the container, place to keep the basic drug, the time period for fermentation, subjective parameters to test elaborately the end point of the procedure and finished product. The application of the prepared medicines (*Asava–Arishta*) is recommended in different disease conditions²⁰.

2. Sushruta Samhita

A number of *Sandhana kalpana* (fermented products) were prescribed for surgical procedures as anesthetic drug as well as a medicine to treat different disease conditions. A total of 21 fermented drugs such as *Asava–Arishta* and 46 *Madya* products named as *Madya*, *Sura*, *Prasanna*, *Jagala*, *Surasava*, *Madhv asava*, *Shukta*, *Dhanyamla* are well documented in this classical text. *Sushruta Samhita* may be credited for addition of botanical ash (*Apamarga*, *Palasha* ash) as ingredients of *Asava–Arishta*. These formulations are prescribed for certain therapeutic purposes. Other essential elements for the preparation of *Asava–Arishta* are also discussed in this text in detail²¹.

3. Ashtanga Hridaya and Ashtang Sangraha

Herbal medicine stream was fully developed in this period; this is reflected in the formulation of different *Sandhana kalpana*. Along with other ingredients, the use of *Dhataki Pushpa* (*Woodfordia fruticosa*) as a fermentation initiator is documented for the first time in *Ashtanga Hridaya*. This could be considered as one of the innovatory steps in pharmaceutical practice to formulate *Sandhana kalpana*. Physicians were well aware of the fermentation techniques, as the container, the place, duration and criteria for testing the product are clearly mentioned in various formulations usually in accordance with previous classics. ‘*Draksha* (grapes), *Ikshu* (sugar cane), *Makshika* (honey), *Shali* (rice), *Vrihi* (grains)

are the five source materials found to be used to prepare *Madya* and *Sandhana kalpana*²².

Draksha is the most acclaimed source material. A total of 17 *Asava-Arishta* are quoted in *Ashtanga Sangraha* and 8 in *Ashtanga Hridaya*.

Kashyapa Samhita

In this classic, the term *Abhishava* is included in seven basic *kalpanas* (dosage forms) to indicate a fermented product. But we did not find a specific process of fermentation mentioned in preparation method. Different formulations are advocated in this time period, which denotes the existence of *Sandhana kalpana* and preparation techniques related to fermented drugs²³.

Chakradatta

Ayamakanjika for the treatment of *grahani* and *siddhamla kalpana* for the treatment of *amavata* and many more products of the *Asava-Arishta* category are quoted in *Chakradatta*. This may be considered as a prominent contribution of *Acharya Chakrapani*²⁴.

Gada Nigraha

A total of 60 *Asava-Arishtas* (fermented drugs) are mentioned in the chapter *Asavadhikar*. Different pharmacodynamic actions of drugs are elaborated, wherein the therapeutic potential of *Sandhana kalpana* is also mentioned²⁵.

Yogaratanakara

In *Yogaratanakar*, a detailed description of *Asava-Arishtas* in *madya kalpana* is given. All these descriptions are similar to the narrations given about *Asava-Arishta* in the previous classical treatise²⁶.

Bhaishajya Ratnavali

The information regarding *Sandhana* formulations is found here as a handbook, which can be simpler in

routine use for the physicians. In the preparation of these drugs, the ingredients, the specific duration to keep the container—for 15 days or 1 month—is mentioned. In this book, a total of 50 *Sandhana kalpanas* are quoted, of which 15 are *Asava*, 29 *Arishta*, 2 *Chukra*, 2 *Sura*, 1 *Shukta*, and 1 *Kanji kalpana*²⁷.

Compilation of formulations of *Asavarishtas* in Ayurvedic Formulary of India

Parts I, II and III of Ayurvedic Formulary of India describes 57 *Asava-Arishta*. part -1 contains 37, part - II contains 3 and part III contains 17 with complete detail of their pharmaceuticals and therapeutics. In this publication by Department of AYUSH, Government of India, the manufacturing process of *Asava-Arishta* are described in the beginning of the chapter and the ingredients (with their part used) and proportion of every formulae are described systematically²⁸.

Material and methods – A number of resources, books and articles including the classical texts have been referred to search the compounds which are prepared by fermentation (*Sandhan Kalpana*) and have been found to influence the gut flora including the motility and have been used in various gut disorders. Efforts are also been made to give references of steps involved in the preparation of these products by using the concepts behind them.

Classification of *Sandhan Kalpana*

Acharya Sushruta first time given specific division of *Sandhan Kalpana*²⁹. (Su.Su. MadhyaVerga 45/175-216)

Sandhana Kalpana is classified under two groups based on the nature of the final product. These are

1. *Madhya Kalpana*
2. *Shukta Kalpana*

<i>Madhya Kalpana</i>	Definition
<i>Sura</i>	The fermented liquor prepared using cooked rice, barley, etc. It is further classified as <i>Prasanna</i> - the clear supernatant fluid of <i>Sura</i> . <i>Kadambari</i> - slightly thicker than <i>Prasanna</i> .

	<i>Jagala-Jagala</i> is thicker and presents lower than <i>Kadambari</i> . <i>Medaka</i> - It is thicker to <i>Jagala</i> . <i>Surabija</i> - Residue leftover after filtration is <i>Vakkasa</i> , <i>Surabija</i> , or <i>Kinw</i>
<i>Sidhu</i>	<i>Sidhu</i> differentiates into two types - <i>Apakwa (Shita rasa) Sidhu</i> - Juice of sweet substances (like sugarcane juice) fermented without boiling. <i>Pakwa Sidhu</i> - Prepared by fermenting sweet juice after boiling them
<i>Varuni</i>	The liquor prepared with the juice of <i>Tala</i> and <i>Kharjura</i>
<i>Asav</i>	The liquor prepared without boiling the drug in water
<i>Arishta</i>	The liquor prepared by boiled/cooked source material.

Shukta kalpana

Shukta	The liquor prepared with roots, tubers, and fruits added with Sneha and Lavana.
<i>Tushodaka</i>	Uncooked <i>Yava</i> is pounded along with <i>Tusha</i> and kept for <i>Sandhana</i> .
<i>Sauvirak</i>	Fermentation of <i>Yava</i> , which is boiled after removing its husk (<i>Nistusha</i>).
<i>Dhanyamala Kanji</i>	A fermented product prepared by <i>dhanya yoni</i> . A fermented product prepared with boiled <i>Kulmasha</i> , <i>Dhanyamanda</i> , etc [Sh. Sa. M. kh. 10 /14 page 242]
<i>Sandaki</i>	A fermented product prepared with radish (<i>Mulaka</i>), mustard (<i>Sarshapa</i>), etc. [Sh. Sa. M. kh. 10 /14 page 242]

Pharmaceutical processing of *asavarishta*:

It involves inspection of the constituents required for preparations composition, *dravadravya* (liquid), *sandhaneeya dravya* (fermenting materials), *prakshepaka dravya* (additives), *madhura dravya* (sweetening agents), *sandhana paatra* (fermentation vessels) used, *samskaras* prior to *sandhana*, method of preparation, the *sandhana sthala* (location) and time (season) of fermentation and the duration of process.

According to *Sharangdhara*, if the quantity of ingredients for fermentation is not specified, one *Drona* (12.288L) of *Drava Dravyas*, and one *Tula* (4.8 kg) of jaggery should be taken. The quantity of honey should be half that of jaggery, while *Prakshepa* should be added one-tenth of the quantity of *Drava Dravya*³⁰.

1. **Aushadha Dravya (drug substance):** This should be taken as per the formulation, especially in case of *Asavas*. The drugs commonly used in *Arishta* are *twak* (bark), *moola* (root) which are *kathina* or *madhyama dravyas* and these are made into *kashaya*. The drugs in *asava* are generally *mrudu*, volatile in nature viz; *karpoora*, *chandana*, *ushira* etc. and these are made as *hima* (cold decoction)/ *phanta* (hot decoction)/ *swarasa* (expressed juice).

There are 9 *yoni*'s for the preparations of *asava arishta* such as *dhanya*(cereals), *phala*(fruit), *mula*(root), *saara* (heart wood), *pushpa*(flower), *kanda*(tuber), *patra*(leaf), *twak*(bark) and *sarkara dravya* (sweetening agents) making at total of 84 in number³¹.

Table

S.No.	Yoni	Number	Example	Formulation example	Refrence
1	<i>Dhanya</i>	06	<i>Shaali</i>	<i>Sura</i>	<i>Sharngadhara</i> ³²
2	<i>Phala</i>	26	<i>Draksha</i>	<i>Draksharishta</i>	<i>Sharngadhara</i> ³³
3	<i>Mula</i>	11	<i>Dashmula</i>	<i>Dasamularishta</i>	<i>Sharngadhara</i> ³⁴
4	<i>Saara</i>	20	<i>Khadira</i>	<i>Khadirarishta</i>	<i>Sharngadhara</i> ³⁵
5	<i>Pushpa</i>	10	<i>Dhataki</i>	<i>Mustkarishtam</i>	<i>Bhaishajya Ratnavali</i> ³⁶
6	<i>Kanda</i>	04	<i>Ikshu</i>	<i>Ikshurasava</i>	<i>Susrutha</i> ³⁷

7	Patra	02	Kumari	Kumaryasava	Sharngadhara ³⁸
8	Twak	04	Kutaja	Kutajarishta	Sharngadhara ³⁹
9	Sharkra	1	Guda	Abhyarishtam	Charaka ⁴⁰

2. **Drava Dravyas:** The Drava Dravyas used for the preparation of *Asavarishtas* are *Jala*, *Swarasa*, *Kwatha*, *Takra*, *Dadhi*, *Gomutra*, *Kanji*, *Dhanyamla*, etc.

Table showing drvadravaya generally used in *Asava arishta*.

Sr. no.	Dravadravaya	Yoga	Reference
1	Jala (water)	Pippalyasava	Sharngadhara ⁴¹
2	Gomutra (cows urine)	Chitrakasava	Astanga Hrudaya ⁴²
3	Dadhi (curd)	Gandeeerasava	Gadanigraha ⁴³
4	Gomayarsava (cowdung)	Gandeeerasava	Gadanigraha ⁴⁴
5	Takra (buttermilk)	Takrarishta	Astanga Hrudaya ⁴⁵
6	Kwatha (decoction)	Dasamoolarishta	Sharngadhara ⁴⁶
7	Swarasa (expressed juice)	Dhatryarishta	Caraka ⁴⁷

Madhura Dravyas (sweetening agent): *Guda* (jaggery), *sharkara* (sugar), *phanita* (molasses), *Matsyandika/ sitopala* (candy sugar) and *honey* (*madhu*) are the major sweetening materials used in *asavarishtas*.

3. Sandhaneeya dravya (fermenting agents):

Even though as such terminology is not available but the well known *sandhaneeya Dravyas* are *dhataki pushpa*⁴⁸, *madhuka pushpa*⁴⁹ which acts as fermenting agent are been included under *prakshepaka dravya* in classics. *Acharya sushruta* mentioned *surabeeja* or *kinwa* as *sandhaneeya dravya*⁵⁰.

All these drugs are provide the inoculum for the fermentation to start, rich amount of yeast cells which facilitates the fermentation process.

Prakshepa Dravya: These are prescribed by Acharyas which flavor the product, and also have precised therapeutic action. *Prakshepaka dravya* (additives). Although *prakshepaka dravyas* form one of the major drug portion in the *asava arishta*, it does not play significant role in fermentation process. *Lavanga*, *ela*, *twak*, *patra*, *nagakesara*, *trikatu* are

commonly used as *praksheepa dravya*, and these are made into *yavakuta* (coarse powder) form and added.

4. Sandhan paatra (Container)

All classical texts recommended the use of earthen containers for the fermentation process, The main intension for using earthen pots is, it maintains the proper temperature and is also inert in nature.

Paatra samaskara (preparation of container):-

Before the *sandhan* process started acharya given a concept of *paatra smasakara*. *Lepan* and *dhupan samaskara* included in *paatra samaskara* these *samskara* done to the vessel prior to the fermentation process.

Lepan is done with *lepan dravyas* conventionally, *lepa* (smearing) using a combination of *lodhra*, *jatamamsi* and *grutha lepa* is applied internally to the vessel prior to the fermentation process⁵¹. The main logic behind this *samskara* may be blocking of minuteness pores in mud pots, and thus maintenance of temperature.

Table *Lepana Dravyas* used in the preparation of *Sandhana Kalpana*

S.No.	Lepana Dravya	Formulation	Reference
I.	Pippali, Chavya, Madhu, Priyangu, Gruta	Phalarishta	Cha.Chi.15/153-157

2.	Ela, Mrunal, Agaru, Chandan	Madhukasava	Cha.Chi.15/153-157
3.	Pippali, Madhu	Loharishta	Su.Chi. 12/12-19
4.	Lodhra, Dhataki	Dantyarishta	ChakradattassssArsha 23-26
5.	Maricha, Madhu	Gandirasava	Ga.Ni.

The fermentation vessels are subjected to *dhoopana*, a process of fumigation to prevent the growth of naturally occurring microorganisms that may contaminate or remove bad odour of *patra* when reused and augments the sterilization of the *sandhana patra*. *Molasses*⁵² or powders of crude drugs like Indian valerian *Chandana*, *karpoora*, *guggulu*, *agaru*, *jatamamsi*, *maricha* are drugs commonly used for this purpose.

5. Temperature and Sandhan Sthala

Sandhana kalpana is placed for the process with minimum temperature variation at the site.

There are few terms described in the context of asavarishta preparations, which specifically indicate the suitability of the place for fermentation, viz., dhanyrashi (heap of barley (Kanakbindu Arishta - Charaka Chikitsa Sthana 7/76-79)), dhanya Madya (keeping inside heap of cereals), yavapalla (heap of barley) and bhounikhatayet (kept under earth) etc. The logic behind this is to maintain uniform temperature during fermentation, as temperature between 25°C – 30°C is considered ideal for proper fermentation⁵³.

d) Duration of Sandhan Kalpana

Jatarasam is the word, which denotes completion of fermentation and formation of appropriate product as per indication quoted in *Sushruta Sutra Sthana* 45/203 and for *Loharishta* - *Sushruta Chikitsa Sthana* 12/12-17. Duration of fermentation varies with formulation, which ranges from 7 days (*Ashtashatarishta* - *Charaka Chikitsa Sthana* 12/32-33) to 180 days (*Guggulu Asava* - *Gada Nigraha* 6/213-221). *Kinva* and slurry are separated through collation process carried out by double-layered cotton cloth for further processing of next batches. Nowadays, electrical filtration press, bacteria filters like advanced techniques are used for large-scale production of these products^{54,55}.

The confirmatory test told in the above mentioned classics are *jatarasam*⁵⁶, *vyaktha amla katuka jatam*⁵⁷, etc. and like other *kalpana gandha varna rasautpatti*⁵⁸ are also described.

Sandhana process (bio-fermentation process)

After doing the *patra samskara* ingredients are mixed properly in the liquids. It should then be filled in the well prepared and recommended container and kept in suitable place recommended for the purpose for a specified period of time for the alcoholic fermentation to start and to go on smoothly. While filling in *sandhana paatra* in ayurvedic classics have specified to keep 1/4th vacant space conducive to the free movement and escape of gases. After the completion of fermentation the necessary tests should be carried out to ensure that fermentation is complete. Then it is filtered in a suitable container

DISCUSSION

United Nations World Health Organization, according to which probiotics are redefined as “live microorganisms which when administered in adequate amounts confer a health benefit on the host.” In relation to food the definition can be adjusted by emphasizing that the beneficial effect is exerted by the microorganisms “when consumed in adequate amounts as part of food”.⁵⁹

Microorganisms involved in the preparation of *Asava-Arishta* for fermentation require water, specific nutritive material as growth promoter and source of energy for their fermenting activity. Carbohydrate acts as the main source of nutrition in the products of *Sandhana kalpana*. The general properties of *asava* are *mana shareera vardhana* (~enriches mind and body) *agni vardhana* (appetizer), *bala vardhana* (~strengthening body), *shoka nashana* (~reduces sadness), *aruchi nashana* (appetizer) and *harsha Pradhana* (~induces happiness). *Arishta* are *laghu* in *paka*, *shreshta* (superior) among *sandhana*

Kalpana and potent than *asava*) Dose of *asavarishta* is one pala⁶⁰. Ancient literature brings out the detailed description of *asavarishta* in vedic and post vedic period. Government of India has also made efforts to compile all the relevant literature into Ayurvedic Formulary of India. Various ancient Ayurvedic texts including Vrihatrayee and others such as Kashyap Samhita, Chakradutta, Yogratnakar etc have classified and described these *Asavarishta* according to nature and processes and also described their uses for gut and other disorders and also for wellbeing. Thus, they identified their presumably Ayurvedic probiotic properties. There have been almost 70 different formulations along with method of preparation mentioned in all these literatures. *Sandhan Kalpana* (fermentation) has been well described in Ayurveda in various texts. There have been specific mentions of process, ingredients, temperature, precautions etc. and primarily include *Sandhan Dravya*, *Drava dravyas*, *Madhur dravyas*, *praksheph dravyas* and *patra sanskaar*, *sandhan sthala* and *jat rasama*.

CONCLUSION

The article brings out the description of probiotics along with detailed description of *Sandhan Kalpana* since the ancient literature. A number of formulations have been identified which are prepared with *Sandhan Kalpana* and have been documented to show beneficial effects in gut disorders. However, there is a need to conduct further studies to look into the microbial flora of these products so that these can fall under the definition of Probiotics and can be rightly called “Ayurvedic probiotics” in the modern context.

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